

Oxford Vaccine Group Vaccine Knowledge Project's Vaccine Ingredient and vaccine safety misinformation exposed

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The Oxford Vaccine Group (OVG) operates a Vaccine Knowledge Project website (1).

Sensitization

The site points out that vaccines can contain numerous proteins such as ovalbumin (egg protein), bovine proteins like bovine serum albumin (BSA), gelatin, chick cell culture proteins, latex etc.

It talks about rare allergic reactions.

Nobel laureate Richet (2) points out that there are two steps in the allergy process. The first protein injection causes the development of allergy (sensitization, no symptoms). The second protein injection a few weeks or more later results in an allergic reaction (elicitation). The most common is IgE mediated sensitization.

So any vaccine that can elicit a reaction will also sensitize (3–5) a person/animal or boost existing sensitization (6).

The site **completely omits this extremely important fact**. As Kursteiner et al. point out, ovalbumin is known as a sensitizing agent (7).

So vaccines **sensitize you to every protein in the vaccine**. Thus **creating the epidemic of allergies** to everything from eggs, to latex to gelatin, to BSA.

The site focuses only on the elicitation part which is rare but omits the sensitization part which is common but asymptomatic (8–10).

“There have been a tiny number of cases of allergic reaction to vaccines containing gelatine”
Proof that intact proteins are present in gelatin and cause the development of gelatin allergy.

“Sorbitol is usually harmless, but people with an allergy to sorbitol, or with rare inherited problems of fructose intolerance, should not receive vaccines containing sorbitol.”
Proof that intact proteins (plant origin(?)) from which sorbitol was sourced) are present and cause the development of allergy to those plant proteins.

“For example, the needle tip of the syringe may be protected with a latex bung. “
Causes the development of latex allergy.

“ there is a purification process reducing these growth supplements to trace amounts. “
So residual proteins are present, not completely removed thus causing the development of allergy to all those proteins. But there is no specification for the safe amount of these protein in the vaccine. Egg protein content varied 100-fold from lot to lot from the same vendor (11). Milk protein 2-fold in just 8 samples (12). This also means **all epidemiological vaccine safety studies are useless**. Researchers

have no clue which product they are studying because product content varies all over the map. I explain the details in my comment published in the Annals of Internal Medicine.

<https://annals.org/aim/fullarticle/2727726/measles-mumps-rubella-vaccination-autism-nationwide-cohort-study>

“Lactose (milk sugar)”

The European Medicines Agency (EMA) found that lactose used in injections was contaminated with milk proteins (13). Thus lactose containing vaccines can cause the development of milk allergy.

Any animal/plant proteins can be present in vaccines

Ovalbumin is a major egg protein and so it is used as a surrogate to measure egg protein content (7). So ovalbumin containing vaccines also contain any of the thousands of other egg proteins. Similarly one can expect all bovine, porcine, chick proteins in vaccines. There are no purity specifications. For example, Japanese researchers found “poorly hydrolyzed” gelatin in vaccines (14).

Due to bovine spongiform encephalopathy (BSE) risk, some bovine products have been replaced with plant derived products. The US National Academy of Medicine reports that vaccines also include sesame/peanut oil, soy, milk and fish proteins (15).

<https://www.verywellhealth.com/what-is-an-autoimmune-disease-189661>

Says: “The autoimmune reaction may be triggered: ... **If a foreign substance that is similar to a normal body substance enters the body.**”

Many animal and plant proteins are very similar to human proteins. So injecting vaccines containing trace amount of animal/plant protein is the definition of “ **a foreign substance that is similar to a normal body substance enters the body**”. So predictably, vaccines cause numerous autoimmune disorders (16). We describe the exact immunological mechanism involved in autoimmunity induced by immunization with homologous xenogeneic antigens (17).

Specifically, chick GAD65 in vaccines cause type 1 diabetes (T1D) (17–19).

Bovine insulin (a cow’s milk protein) in vaccines cause T1D (20).

Bovine folate receptor alpha (a cow’s milk protein) in vaccines cause autism (21).

Animal/plant aquaporin-4 containing vaccines cause neuromyelitis optica spectrum disorders (NMOSD) (16).

Animal acetylcholine receptor protein containing vaccines cause myasthenia gravis (22).

The list is endless.

Prions

The site talks about BSE risk of bovine products. Yeast proteins are prionogenic (23). The site points out that Hepatitis B and HPV vaccines contain yeast proteins.

“A tiny quantity of yeast protein may remain in the 6-in-1 vaccine (Infanrix Hexa) and the Hepatitis B vaccines used in the UK”

But there is no mention of prionogenic yeast proteins and the damage they cause including Alzheimer’s and type 2 diabetes (24,25).

Aeroallergens

Another vaccine ingredient they completely missed is aeroallergens. World Health Organization (WHO) clean room specifications allow thousands of dust particles per cubic meter. So fine dust that includes pollen sub particles, house dust mite, roach feces, pet dander proteins are present in vaccines. Many vaccines are also offered in multi-dose vials or require reconstitution. This means even more aeroallergen contamination at the end user site. The result is sensitization to all these aeroallergens which predictably causes the asthma, GERD and seasonal/perennial allergy epidemics (26).

Aluminum and other adjuvants

Talking about aluminum adjuvant they write: “They act as adjuvants, strengthening and lengthening the immune response to the vaccine. “. So aluminum adjuvants, boost the immune response to the trace amounts of all the proteins above thus creating allergies to all of them. Aluminum adjuvants also provide the innate immune system costimulation required to activate T cells that target animal proteins, thus resulting in autoimmunity (17).

Eating aluminum does not produce the above effects. It is therefore ridiculous that the site compares such intramuscular injected aluminum based adjuvants that are specially formulated for their adjuvant properties, with ingested aluminum in baby formula milk.

The safety of aluminum adjuvants is being currently studied by Cochrane. Please see my comments included in the Cochrane articles on the study limitations (27,28).

Conclusion

The OVG Vaccine Knowledge Project’s Vaccine Ingredient information is wrong about vaccine safety claims. It is incomplete. Their claim of being “Authoritative” is laughable.

If this site is a product “overseen by academic staff at the cutting edge of vaccine research” there is little hope for safe vaccines.

The site needs a complete overhaul to reflect reality and science. There are two possible explanations for this misinformation. The OVG academic staff is incompetent or they know the problems and have decided to mislead the public. Both are extremely troubling.

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